

Dipole Moments of some Triarylsarsines, Triarylsarsine Oxides and Triarylsarsine Sulphides

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Manuscript received 20 June 1988, revised 10 October 1990, accepted 21 November 1990

The dipole moments of six triarylsarsines, five triarylsarsine oxides and four triarylsarsine sulphides have been determined. A comparative analysis of the dipole moment of tri-*p*-anisylarsine with that of triphenylarsine reveals considerable conjugative interaction of the anisyl groups with arsenic atom.

In the present investigation, the dipole moments of six triarylsarsines and some of their oxides and sulphides have been determined as the available dipole moment data on this group of compounds was found to be meagre. It has also been thought of interest to examine the possibility of *d*-orbital resonance in organoarsenic compounds.

Experimental

The apparatus used, definitions of symbols used and the method of calculating dipole moments were as reported earlier¹.

The compounds used were prepared as described in the literature².

Results and Discussion

In anisole the angle of the dipole axis to the 1-4 axis of the ring is 75° (calculated from the moments: anisole, 1.25 D; *p*-dimethoxybenzene, 1.71 D)³, assuming the negative end of the dipole is directed towards the ring. The dipole moment of tri-*p*-anisylarsine is calculated making the following assumptions: (i) the moment of *p*-anisyl group is

the same as that of anisole, and (ii) the arsenic bond angles in tri-*p*-anisylarsine remain the same as those in triphenylarsine. Since the dipole axes in triphenylarsine and tri-*p*-anisylarsine are the same, the dipole moment (μ) of the latter can be given as

$$\begin{aligned}\mu &= \mu_{\text{Ph}_3\text{As}} + (3 \times 1.25 \cos 75^\circ \cos 69 \frac{1}{2}^\circ) \\ &= 1.13 + 0.34 \text{ D} \\ &= 1.47 \text{ D}\end{aligned}$$

where 69 1/2° is the calculated angle between the dipole axis and Ph-As bonds. The experimental value (2.55 D) is 1.08 D higher than the calculated one. This large difference can only be explained on the basis of considerable electronic interaction between the arsenic atom and the *p*-anisyl groups, the former acting as an electron-acceptor with the in-coming electron going into one of the vacant *d*-orbitals in its valence shell.

Triphenylarsine oxide seems to be the only arsine oxide whose dipole moment is recorded in the literature⁴. No dipole moment data are available for arsine sulphides. The values obtained for some triarylsarsine oxides and sulphides in the present study are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—POLARISATION DATA IN BENZENE SOLUTION AT 30°

Compd.	α	$-\beta$	γ	∞P_2 ml	R_D ml	μ^* D
(C ₆ H ₅) ₃ As	0.827	0.389 2	0.397 4	117.4	91.6	1.13 ^a
(<i>o</i> -CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄) ₃ As	0.427	0.350 9	0.348 6	110.9	96.1	0.86
(<i>m</i> -CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄) ₃ As	0.900	0.339 9	0.325 2	143.3	104.3	1.39
(<i>p</i> -CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄) ₃ As	1.070	0.332 0	0.347 0	155.5	109.3	1.52 ^b
(<i>p</i> -CH ₃ O.C ₆ H ₄) ₃ As	2.030	0.388 9	0.306 3	242.4	111.5	2.55
(<i>o</i> -CH ₃ O.C ₆ H ₄) ₃ As	1.849	0.387 3	0.320 5	229.0	109.6	2.44
(C ₆ H ₅) ₃ AsO	11.170	0.414 1	0.285 4	754.5	87.0	5.76 ^c
(<i>o</i> -CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄) ₃ AsO	8.630	0.411 8	0.292 1	680.8	99.1	5.38
(<i>m</i> -CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄) ₃ AsO	9.310	0.415 9	0.373 8	724.4	104.4	5.55
(<i>p</i> -CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄) ₃ AsO.H ₂ O ^d	11.930	0.381 5	0.260 2	954.0	105.0	6.50
(<i>p</i> -CH ₃ O.C ₆ H ₄) ₃ AsO.H ₂ O ^d	8.451	0.402 0	0.258 7	786.9	115.5	5.78
(C ₆ H ₅) ₃ AsS	9.369	0.490 5	0.440 7	670.2	93.9	5.35
(<i>m</i> -CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄) ₃ AsS	8.906	0.425 6	0.378 9	725.7	108.3	5.54
(<i>p</i> -CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄) ₃ AsS	9.891	0.396 4	0.380 2	800.3	111.6	5.85
(<i>p</i> -CH ₃ O.C ₆ H ₄) ₃ AsS	9.627	0.493 3	0.422 4	867.3	117.1	6.11

*Lit. values: ^a1.07 D⁵; ^b1.74 D⁶; ^c5.54 D⁴. ^dExists as dihydroxide.

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The calculation of the As→O bond moment in triphenylarsine oxide is simple. The change, which occurs when triphenylarsine is converted into its oxide, is the vector along the direction of the new bond, supposing that when the latter is formed, the moment of the donor molecule remains unchanged. This assumption is not very accurate but it will not lead to any serious error. For symmetrical arsines the new bond is along the axis of symmetry. So the required vector is the algebraic difference of the moments of triphenylarsine and its oxide. Thus the As→O bond moment in $(C_6H_5)_3AsO$ is $5.76 - 1.13 = 4.63$ D.

In the same way the As→S bond moment (4.22 D) in triphenylarsine sulphide can be obtained by subtracting the moment of triphenylarsine from that of its sulphide. In the case of tri-*p*-anisylarsine sulphide the moment of each CH_3O group acts at an angle of 75° to the 1-4 axis of the anisyl group. Assuming that all the bond angles of As in tri-*p*-anisylarsine sulphide to be tetrahedral, the dipole moment, $\mu = 5.70$ D. The calculated as well as the observed dipole moments of the arsine oxides and sulphides are shown in Table 2.

The agreement between the observed and calculated values in all cases except for tri-*p*-anisylarsine sulphide is remarkably good. The observed moment of tri-*p*-anisylarsine sulphide is 0.41 D higher than

TABLE 2—OBSERVED AND CALCULATED DIPOLE MOMENTS OF TRIARYLARSINE OXIDES AND SULPHIDES

Compd	Dipole moment (D)		$\Delta\mu$
	Obs	Calcd *	
$(m\text{-CH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_4)_3\text{AsO}$	5.55	5.69	-0.14
$(o\text{-CH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_4)_3\text{AsO}$	5.38	5.31	+0.07
$(p\text{-CH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_4)_3\text{AsS}$	5.85	5.72	+0.13
$(m\text{-CH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_4)_3\text{AsS}$	5.54	5.54	0
$(p\text{-CH}_3\text{O.C}_6\text{H}_4)_3\text{AsS}$	6.11	5.70	+0.41

*Assuming free rotation of the aryl groups.

the calculated value. This is due to the conjugative interaction of *p*-anisyl groups with As→S.

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